

TEACHING PROFESSIONALLY-ORIENTED INFORMATIVE READING IN ENGLISH AT UNIVERSITIES

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Annotation: An important task of the modern higher education system is the training of a specialist with professional competence. As a rule, such a specialist is able to understand the information flows of his field of activity. At the same time, the most accessible way to obtain the necessary information is to read.

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Speaking of professionally-oriented reading at higher educational institutions, it should be noted that a young specialist needs to possess not so much a reference as an informative type of reading, since reference reading implies only a general view of the main topic of the text, while informative reading involves extracting semantic information from a foreign text. It is informative foreign language reading that is necessary for the implementation of cognitive activity with its help. That is why teachers of higher educational institutions should pay special attention to the development of the skills of mature professionally-oriented foreign language informative reading among students at the initial stage of their studies at the university. The result of reading is the fixation in various forms of what is understood for oneself and for others. The types of fixation depend, first of all, on the goals of a particular type of reading in each particular case, as well as on the practical value of the information and its further use. professional competence foreign language reading. The solution to the problem of fixing what has been read can be some techniques of the technology of developing critical thinking through reading and writing, such as "Insert", "Cluster", "Fishbone".

A feature of the technology is the need to follow three phases: evocation (challenge), realization (comprehension of new information) and reflection (how to reflect). At the first stage, the task is not only to activate and interest the student, but also to "evoke" existing knowledge or create associations on the issue under study. At the second stage, there is a direct work with information so as to make reading or listening meaningful. At the third stage, information is analyzed, interpreted, and creatively processed. In relation to foreign language classes, it is

possible to correlate the stages of new technology and the classical stages of working with text (pre-text, text and post-text). The "cluster" techniques, the "Insert" table, the "Fishbone", built in the logic of "challenge-comprehension-reflection", contribute to the development of reflexive abilities, help to master the ability to learn independently. When choosing the techniques listed above, it is necessary to take into account the purpose and type of foreign language professionally-oriented reading, the structure of the text and its communicative type (description, narration, reasoning). There are three subspecies of informative reading: evaluative-informative, appropriative-informative and creative-informative. During evaluative and informative reading, the reader's attention is directed to assessing the completeness, novelty, importance, usefulness of the information contained in a foreign language text, and the possibility of its use in future activities. In this case, it is advisable to use the "Insert" table or the "Fishbone" graphic information organizer to fix the text information. An example of work on the development of evaluative and informative reading skills can be the following algorithm for working with professionally-directed text "What Kind of Thing Is Moore's Law?" by students of technical specialties. At the challenge stage, students in the form of a "brainstorming session" discuss what they know about Moore's law and why it is important. Then, at the comprehension stage, students read the text and mark it with special icons according to the "Insert" method (already knew, + - new knowledge, - - thought differently, ? - doubt/there is a question). At the stage of reflection, students in groups discuss which ideas expressed by the author in the text aroused their special interest /doubts / questions; which facts were new, and which they knew before reading the text. In the future, the completed "Insert" table can be used as a plan for retelling the text.

In the process of appropriating and informative reading, the original information is assigned to the readers in the form in which it is submitted by the author. In the process of assigning and informative reading, you can use such a method of working with text as compiling a "cluster". The technique consists in the allocation of semantic units of the text and their graphic design in a certain order in the form of a "bunch". Using the example of working with a technical text, it looks like this: at the challenge stage, students get acquainted with a new vocabulary, and discuss a possible idea of the text, guided by new words and phrases; at the stage of comprehension, students read the text, while drawing up a diagram of the content of the text on key and secondary facts in the form of a

"bunch". The resulting cluster can be used at the stage of reflection in preparation for retelling.

The application of the methods of the modern technologies can not only help the teacher to assess the ability of students to carry out professionally-oriented informative foreign language reading, but also show students that reading in English class carries not only a training function, but also develops the skills of obtaining and processing professionally relevant information. The use of the methods of the reading technology will make it possible to achieve a more complete understanding of the text, and also, which is especially important for a future specialist, to use the information obtained in further professional activities.

References

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